

Enrichment_comparisons

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All code required to run gene list comparisons. # packages

```
library(pacman)
p_unload(dplyr)
p_load(purrr, tidyverse, TCseq, magrittr, tidyr, readr, data.table,
       clusterProfiler, hdWGCNA, DOSE, org.Hs.eg.db)
p_load(dplyr)
```

1. Comparing Enriched Terms Between Disease Gene Lists

Goal: Look at overlap in HPO enrichments between neurodevelopmental and neurological gene lists.

```
HPO_enrich <- read.csv("./scratch/sanitycheck/enrichments/neuropsych_genelist_enrichments_HPO_0.05padj_1")

# Filter the dataframe for descriptions that appear more
# than once
repeated_descriptions <- HPO_enrich %>%
  group_by(Description) %>%
  filter(n() > 1) %>%
  pull(Description) %>%
  unique()

df_filtered <- HPO_enrich %>%
  filter(Description %in% repeated_descriptions)

descriptions_by_cluster <- HPO_enrich %>%
  group_by(Cluster) %>%
  summarise(Descriptions = list(unique(Description))) %>%
  deframe()

intersect_neuroneurodev <- intersect(descriptions_by_cluster[["SNV_neuro1"]],
  descriptions_by_cluster[["SNV_neurodev"]])
intersect_psychneurodev <- intersect(descriptions_by_cluster[["SNV_psych"]],
  descriptions_by_cluster[["SNV_neurodev"]])
intersect_psychneuro1 <- intersect(descriptions_by_cluster[["SNV_psych"]],
  descriptions_by_cluster[["SNV_neuro1"]])

print(intersect_neuroneurodev)
```

[1] "Abnormal hindbrain morphology"
[2] "Abnormal metencephalon morphology"
[3] "Abnormal cerebellum morphology"
[4] "Abnormal nervous system electrophysiology"
[5] "Abnormal cerebral subcortex morphology"
[6] "Brain atrophy"
[7] "Abnormal cerebral white matter morphology"
[8] "Atrophy/Degeneration affecting the cerebrum"
[9] "Abnormal corpus callosum morphology"
[10] "Cerebral atrophy"
[11] "EEG with generalized epileptiform discharges"
[12] "Abnormality of central nervous system electrophysiology"
[13] "Thin corpus callosum"
[14] "Interictal epileptiform activity"
[15] "Interictal EEG abnormality"
[16] "EEG abnormality"
[17] "Hypsarrhythmia"
[18] "Abnormal cortical gyration"
[19] "Motor seizure"
[20] "Abnormality of neuronal migration"
[21] "Epileptic spasm"
[22] "Aplasia/Hypoplasia of the corpus callosum"
[23] "Abnormal myelination"
[24] "Infantile spasms"
[25] "Aplasia/Hypoplasia of the cerebellum"
[26] "Tonic seizure"
[27] "Aplasia/Hypoplasia of the cerebrum"
[28] "Abnormal cerebellar vermis morphology"
[29] "Generalized-onset seizure"
[30] "Bilateral tonic-clonic seizure"
[31] "Non-motor seizure"
[32] "Cerebellar hypoplasia"
[33] "Dialeptic seizure"
[34] "Generalized hypotonia"
[35] "Myoclonic seizure"
[36] "Abnormality of the lower limb"
[37] "EEG with spike-wave complexes"
[38] "Lissencephaly"
[39] "Cerebellar vermis hypoplasia"
[40] "Atonic seizure"
[41] "Abnormal foot morphology"
[42] "Pachygyria"
[43] "Abnormal cerebral ventricle morphology"
[44] "Aplasia/Hypoplasia of the cerebellar vermis"
[45] "Microcephaly"
[46] "Ventriculomegaly"
[47] "Ptosis"
[48] "Febrile seizure (within the age range of 3 months to 6 years)"
[49] "Infection-related seizure"
[50] "Seizure precipitated by febrile infection"
[51] "Generalized non-motor (absence) seizure"
[52] "Decreased head circumference"
[53] "Axial hypotonia"
[54] "Infantile onset"

```
## [55] "Fetal anomaly"
## [56] "Visual impairment"
## [57] "Abnormality of prenatal development or birth"
## [58] "Hypoplasia of the corpus callosum"
## [59] "Agenesis of corpus callosum"
## [60] "Congenital onset"
## [61] "Severe global developmental delay"
## [62] "Secondary microcephaly"
## [63] "Abnormality of skull size"
## [64] "Abnormal curvature of the vertebral column"
## [65] "Intellectual disability, profound"
## [66] "Long face"
## [67] "Feeding difficulties in infancy"
## [68] "Intellectual disability, mild"
```

```
print(intersect_psychneurodev)
```

```
## NULL
```

```
print(intersect_psychneuro1)
```

```
## NULL
```

2. Disease gene List intersects with genes in TCSeq Gene Clusters

Purpose: Look at gene lists in the context of the disease enrichments from cell type time clusters

Read in disease gene lists

```
# read in the gene lists:
psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/psych_allgenes_list.txt")
neuro1 <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/neuro1_allgenes_list.txt")
neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/neurodev_allgenes_list.txt")
```

Define output directory

```
outdir <- "./results/gene_comparisons"
```

Function to process the summary enrichment files and save intersects

```
process_summary_enrichment <- function(enrich_type, summary_file) {
  if (file.exists(summary_file)) {
    message(paste0("Processing ", enrich_type, " summary enrichment file for disease gene intersects."))

    enrich_data <- read.csv(summary_file)
    enrich_data$genes <- lapply(strsplit(enrich_data$geneID,
      "/"), function(x) paste("\", x, "\", sep = ""))
    enrich_data$genes <- sapply(enrich_data$genes, function(x) paste(x,
```

```

collapse = ", ")

geneinfo <- data.frame(Cluster = enrich_data$Cluster,
  ID = enrich_data$ID, Description = enrich_data$Description,
  Genes = enrich_data$geneID)

geneinfo$Genes <- strsplit(geneinfo$Genes, "/")
geneinfo$Psych_DisgeneIntersect <- lapply(geneinfo$Genes,
  function(row_genes) intersect(psych, row_genes))
geneinfo$Neurodev_DisgeneIntersect <- lapply(geneinfo$Genes,
  function(row_genes) intersect(neurodev, row_genes))
geneinfo$Neurol_DisgeneIntersect <- lapply(geneinfo$Genes,
  function(row_genes) intersect(neurol, row_genes))

# fwrite(geneinfo, file = paste0(outdir, '/TCSeq_',
# enrich_type, '_disgene_intersect.csv'))
} else {
  message(paste0("Summary ", enrich_type, " enrichment file does not exist"))
}
}

```

Process the summary enrichment files for DGN and HPO

```

process_summary_enrichment("DGN", "./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/20240606_DGN_summary_enrichment.csv")
process_summary_enrichment("HPO", "./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/20240606_HPO_summary_enrichment.csv")
rm(list = ls())

```

3. Disease gene list intersects with genes in hdWGCNA module enrichments

Purpose: Look at gene lists in the context of enrichments from hdWGCNA gene co-expression modules

```

outdir <- "./results/gene_comparisons"
psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/psych_allgenes_list.txt")
neurol <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/neurol_allgenes_list.txt")
neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/neurodev_allgenes_list.txt")

```

```

process_summary_enrichment_files <- function(enrich_file, enrich_type) {
  if (file.exists(enrich_file)) {
    message(paste0("Processing ", enrich_type, " summary enrichment file: ",
      enrich_file))

    enrich_data <- read_csv(enrich_file)

    # Assuming 'Name' column includes both cell type
    # and cluster information
    enrich_data$Genes <- strsplit(enrich_data$geneID, "/")
  }
}

```

```

enrich_data$Psych_DisgeneIntersect <- lapply(enrich_data$Genes,
      function(row_genes) intersect(psych, row_genes))
enrich_data$Neurodev_DisgeneIntersect <- lapply(enrich_data$Genes,
      function(row_genes) intersect(neurodev, row_genes))
enrich_data$Neurol_DisgeneIntersect <- lapply(enrich_data$Genes,
      function(row_genes) intersect(neurol, row_genes))

# fwrite(enrich_data, file = paste0(outdir,
# '/hdWGCNA_intersect_summary_', enrich_type,
# '.csv'))
} else {
  message(paste0("No summary enrichment file found for ",
    enrich_type))
}
}

```

```

summary_files <- list(HPO = "./results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/summary_enrichments/CLR_HPO",
  DGN = "./results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/summary_enrichments/CLR_DGN_enrichments_allce")

for (enrich_type in names(summary_files)) {
  enrich_file <- summary_files[[enrich_type]]
  process_summary_enrichment_files(enrich_file, enrich_type)
}

```

4. Calculating Jaccard scores in module/cluster enrichments vs disease gene lists

determine similarity scores between the enriched gene sets for modules and clusters, and the disease gene lists.

```

# Read in the disease gene lists
psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/psych_allgenes_list.txt")
neurol <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/neurol_allgenes_list.txt")
neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Gene_symbols/neurodev_allgenes_list.txt")

# Read in enrichment summaries for both TCSeq and hdWGCNA
module_DGN <- read.csv("./results/gene_comparisons/hdWGCNA_intersect_summary_DGN.csv")
module_HPO <- read.csv("./results/gene_comparisons/hdWGCNA_intersect_summary_HPO.csv")
cluster_DGN <- read.csv("./results/gene_comparisons/TCSeq_DGN_disgene_intersect.csv")
cluster_HPO <- read.csv("./results/gene_comparisons/TCSeq_HPO_disgene_intersect.csv")

# Define output directory
outdir <- "./results/gene_comparisons"

# Define Jaccard Index calculation function
calculate_jaccard_index <- function(genes1, genes2) {
  genes1_set <- unique(strsplit(genes1, "\\|")[[1]])
  genes2_set <- unique(genes2)
  intersection <- length(intersect(genes1_set, genes2_set))
  union <- length(union(genes1_set, genes2_set))
}

```

```

    jaccard_index <- intersection/union
    return(jaccard_index)
}

# Calculate Jaccard Index for each row of DGN and HPO (Just
# the genes in the cells for the enrichment terms) For
# TCSeq DGN
cluster_DGN$JaccardIndex_Neurol <- sapply(cluster_DGN$Genes,
    function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurol))
cluster_DGN$JaccardIndex_Neurodev <- sapply(cluster_DGN$Genes,
    function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurodev))
cluster_DGN$JaccardIndex_Psych <- sapply(cluster_DGN$Genes, function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes,
    psych))

# For TCSeq HPO
cluster_HPO$JaccardIndex_Neurol <- sapply(cluster_HPO$Genes,
    function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurol))
cluster_HPO$JaccardIndex_Neurodev <- sapply(cluster_HPO$Genes,
    function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurodev))
cluster_HPO$JaccardIndex_Psych <- sapply(cluster_HPO$Genes, function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes,
    psych))

# For hdWGCNA DGN
module_DGN$JaccardIndex_Neurol <- sapply(module_DGN$Genes, function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes,
    neurol))
module_DGN$JaccardIndex_Neurodev <- sapply(module_DGN$Genes,
    function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurodev))
module_DGN$JaccardIndex_Psych <- sapply(module_DGN$Genes, function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes,
    psych))

# For hdWGCNA HPO
module_HPO$JaccardIndex_Neurol <- sapply(module_HPO$Genes, function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes,
    neurol))
module_HPO$JaccardIndex_Neurodev <- sapply(module_HPO$Genes,
    function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurodev))
module_HPO$JaccardIndex_Psych <- sapply(module_HPO$Genes, function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes,
    psych))

# Save the initial Jaccard Index results
# write_csv(cluster_DGN, file = paste0(outdir,
# '/TCSeq_DGN_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv'))
# write_csv(cluster_HPO, file = paste0(outdir,
# '/TCSeq_HPO_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv'))
# write_csv(module_DGN, file = paste0(outdir,
# '/hdWGCNA_DGN_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv'))
# write_csv(module_HPO, file = paste0(outdir,
# '/hdWGCNA_HPO_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv'))

# Process HPO Enrichment with Full Gene List for Each Term
phenotype_to_genes <- read_tsv("./HPO_dat/phenotype_to_genes.txt") %>%
    dplyr::select(-disease_id) %>%
    distinct()

```

```

# Grabbing relevant terms for TCSeq HPO
HPO_terms_TCSeq <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  filter(hpo_id %in% cluster_HPO$ID) %>%
  group_by(hpo_id) %>%
  summarise(gene_symbol = paste(gene_symbol, collapse = "|"),
            .groups = "drop")

# Calculate Jaccard Index with all genes in the term for
# TCSeq HPO
HPO_terms_TCSeq$JaccardIndex_Neurol_All <- sapply(HPO_terms_TCSeq$gene_symbol,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurol))
HPO_terms_TCSeq$JaccardIndex_Neurodev_All <- sapply(HPO_terms_TCSeq$gene_symbol,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurodev))
HPO_terms_TCSeq$JaccardIndex_Psych_All <- sapply(HPO_terms_TCSeq$gene_symbol,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, psych))

# Rename columns for clarity
HPO_terms_TCSeq <- dplyr::rename(HPO_terms_TCSeq, ID = hpo_id,
  allGenes_term = gene_symbol)
cluster_HPO <- dplyr::rename(cluster_HPO, genes_enrichment = Genes)

# Merge HPO with full term gene list for TCSeq and save
joined_HPO_TCSeq <- left_join(cluster_HPO, HPO_terms_TCSeq, by = "ID")
# write_csv(joined_HPO_TCSeq, paste0(outdir,
# '/TCSeq_HPO_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv'))

# Grabbing relevant terms for hdWGCNA HPO
HPO_terms_hdWGCNA <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  filter(hpo_id %in% module_HPO$ID) %>%
  group_by(hpo_id) %>%
  summarise(gene_symbol = paste(gene_symbol, collapse = "|"),
            .groups = "drop")

# Calculate Jaccard Index with all genes in the term for
# hdWGCNA HPO
HPO_terms_hdWGCNA$JaccardIndex_Neurol_All <- sapply(HPO_terms_hdWGCNA$gene_symbol,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurol))
HPO_terms_hdWGCNA$JaccardIndex_Neurodev_All <- sapply(HPO_terms_hdWGCNA$gene_symbol,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurodev))
HPO_terms_hdWGCNA$JaccardIndex_Psych_All <- sapply(HPO_terms_hdWGCNA$gene_symbol,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, psych))

# Rename columns for clarity
HPO_terms_hdWGCNA <- dplyr::rename(HPO_terms_hdWGCNA, ID = hpo_id,
  allGenes_term = gene_symbol)
module_HPO <- dplyr::rename(module_HPO, genes_enrichment = Genes)

# Merge HPO with full term gene list for hdWGCNA and save
joined_HPO_hdWGCNA <- left_join(module_HPO, HPO_terms_hdWGCNA,
  by = "ID")
# write_csv(joined_HPO_hdWGCNA, paste0(outdir,
# '/hdWGCNA_HPO_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv'))

```

```

# Process DGN Enrichment with Full Gene List for Each Term
data("DGN_PATHID2EXTID")

# Create a dataframe of the DGN pathways with their
# associated genes
large_list_df <- map_df(names(DGN_PATHID2EXTID), ~tibble(ID = .x,
  Genes = list(DGN_PATHID2EXTID[[.x]])))

# Filter to include only the relevant IDs and transform the
# gene lists into slash-separated strings for TCSeq DGN
DGN_results_TCSeq <- large_list_df %>%
  filter(ID %in% cluster_DGN$ID) %>%
  mutate(Genes = map_chr(Genes, ~paste(.x, collapse = "|")))

# Map Entrez IDs to Symbols for each list element
map_entrez_to_symbol <- function(entrez_ids) {
  genes <- bitr(geneID = entrez_ids, fromType = "ENTREZID",
    toType = "SYMBOL", OrgDb = org.Hs.eg.db, drop = FALSE) %>%
    drop_na() %>%
    pull(SYMBOL)
  paste(genes, collapse = "|")
}
DGN_results_TCSeq$GeneSymbols <- sapply(strsplit(as.character(DGN_results_TCSeq$Genes),
  "\\|"), map_entrez_to_symbol)

# Calculate Jaccard Index with all genes in the term for
# TCSeq DGN
DGN_results_TCSeq$JaccardIndex_Neuro1_All <- sapply(DGN_results_TCSeq$GeneSymbols,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neuro1))
DGN_results_TCSeq$JaccardIndex_Neurodev_All <- sapply(DGN_results_TCSeq$GeneSymbols,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurodev))
DGN_results_TCSeq$JaccardIndex_Psych_All <- sapply(DGN_results_TCSeq$GeneSymbols,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, psych))

# Rename columns for clarity
DGN_results_TCSeq <- dplyr::rename(DGN_results_TCSeq, allGenes_term = GeneSymbols)
cluster_DGN <- dplyr::rename(cluster_DGN, genes_enrichment = Genes)

# Merge DGN with full term gene list for TCSeq and save
joined_DGN_TCSeq <- left_join(cluster_DGN, DGN_results_TCSeq,
  by = "ID")
# write_csv(joined_DGN_TCSeq, paste0(outdir,
# '/TCSeq_DGN_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv'))

# Filter to include only the relevant IDs and transform the
# gene lists into slash-separated strings for hdWGCNA DGN
DGN_results_hdWGCNA <- large_list_df %>%
  filter(ID %in% module_DGN$ID) %>%
  mutate(Genes = map_chr(Genes, ~paste(.x, collapse = "|")))

DGN_results_hdWGCNA$GeneSymbols <- sapply(strsplit(as.character(DGN_results_hdWGCNA$Genes),
  "\\|"), map_entrez_to_symbol)

```

```

# Calculate Jaccard Index with all genes in the term for
# hdWGCNA DGN
DGN_results_hdWGCNA$JaccardIndex_Neuro1_All <- sapply(DGN_results_hdWGCNA$GeneSymbols,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neuro1))
DGN_results_hdWGCNA$JaccardIndex_Neurodev_All <- sapply(DGN_results_hdWGCNA$GeneSymbols,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, neurodev))
DGN_results_hdWGCNA$JaccardIndex_Psych_All <- sapply(DGN_results_hdWGCNA$GeneSymbols,
  function(genes) calculate_jaccard_index(genes, psych))

# Rename columns for clarity
DGN_results_hdWGCNA <- dplyr::rename(DGN_results_hdWGCNA, allGenes_term = GeneSymbols)
module_DGN <- dplyr::rename(module_DGN, genes_enrichment = Genes)

# Merge DGN with full term gene list for hdWGCNA and save
joined_DGN_hdWGCNA <- left_join(module_DGN, DGN_results_hdWGCNA,
  by = "ID")
# write_csv(joined_DGN_hdWGCNA, paste0(outdir,
# '/hdWGCNA_DGN_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv'))

```

5. Genes in modules vs clusters

Compare to what extent genes following a similar trajectory in one cell (TCSeq) overlap with co-regulated genes (hdWGCNA) in the same cell type. This will allow us to link the two figures and hopefully aid in the interpretation.

Get celltype list & define outdirs.

```

outdir <- "./results/gene_comparisons"
outdir_tcseq <- "./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/"
outdir_hdwcna <- "./results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/"
celltypes <- list.dirs(path = outdir_hdwcna, full.names = FALSE,
  recursive = FALSE)
elements_2_remove = c("summary_enrichments")
celltypes = celltypes[!(celltypes %in% elements_2_remove)]

```

For each celltype, read in module-gene info, and cluster-gene info. calculate overlaps. Make table. This will be a comparison of ALL genes in modules and ALL genes in clusters

```

for (cell in celltypes) {
  outdir <- "./results/gene_comparisons/celltype_mod_clust_overlap/"
  message(paste0("Reading in Module Connectivity for ", cell))
  cluster_seurat <- readRDS(paste0(outdir_hdwcna, cell, "/",
    cell, "Module_connectivity.RDS"))

  # Get the modules- remove grey modules as these are
  # genes not associated to a module
  modules <- GetModules(cluster_seurat) %>%
    filter(module != "grey") # Remove grey modules

  # rearrange data
  genes_by_module <- modules %>%

```

```

dplyr::select(gene_name, module) %>%
distinct() %>%
group_by(module) %>%
summarise(gene_names = list(gene_name), .groups = "drop")

message(paste0("Reading in Temporal Clusters for ", cell))

timeclustera <- readRDS(paste0(outdir_tcseq, "/", cell, "/",
cell, "timeclustera.RDS"))

geneinfo <- data.frame(SYMBOL = names(timeclustera@clusterRes@cluster),
cluster = paste0("Cluster_", as.character(timeclustera@clusterRes@cluster)))
symbol_to_entrez <- bitr(geneinfo$SYMBOL, fromType = "SYMBOL",
toType = "ENTREZID", OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db", drop = FALSE) %>%
group_by(SYMBOL) %>%
dplyr::slice(1) %>%
ungroup()

geneinfo <- full_join(geneinfo, symbol_to_entrez, by = "SYMBOL")

# And now generate the gene cluster lists.
message("Generating gene cluster lists")
genelists <- list()
genelists <- sapply(unique(geneinfo$cluster), FUN = function(x) {
genes <- geneinfo %>%
filter(cluster == x) %>%
pull(ENTREZID)
genelists <- append(genelists, list(genes))
})

background <- geneinfo$ENTREZID

# Initialize an empty data frame to store intersection
# results
intersection_df <- data.frame(module = character(), cluster = character(),
module_gene_count = integer(), cluster_gene_count = integer(),
intersected_gene_count = integer(), intersected_genes = character(),
stringsAsFactors = FALSE)

for (module_name in unique(genes_by_module$module)) {
module_genes <- unlist(genes_by_module$gene_names[genes_by_module$module ==
module_name])
module_gene_count <- length(module_genes)

# Sort cluster names based on their numerical part
sorted_cluster_names <- names(genelists)[order(as.numeric(gsub("Cluster_",
"", names(genelists))))]

for (cluster_name in sorted_cluster_names) {
cluster_genes <- genelists[[cluster_name]]
cluster_gene_count <- length(cluster_genes)

```

```

intersected_genes <- intersect(module_genes, cluster_genes)
intersected_gene_count <- length(intersected_genes)

# Concatenate intersected genes into a single
# string
genes_str <- paste(intersected_genes, collapse = ",")

# Append results to the data frame
intersection_df <- rbind(intersection_df, data.frame(module = module_name,
  module_gene_count = module_gene_count, cluster = cluster_name,
  cluster_gene_count = cluster_gene_count, intersected_gene_count = intersected_gene_count,
  intersected_genes = genes_str))

}
}

# Now save the data frame as a CSV file
csv_filename <- paste0(outdir, cell, "_module_cluster_intersection_results.csv")
# write.csv(intersection_df, csv_filename, row.names =
# FALSE) Optional: Clear variables that are specific to
# this iteration to save memory
rm(list = setdiff(ls(), c("celltypes", "outdir_hdwgcn",
  "outdir_tcseq")))
}

```

in a similar vein, it would be great to compare the genes driving significant enrichments in the modules and clusters. Let's do it!

```

outdir <- "./results/gene_comparisons/"
modules <- read_csv(paste0(outdir, "hdWGCNA_HPO_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv"))
clusters <- read_csv(paste0(outdir, "TCSeq_HPO_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv"))
dis_clust_intersect <- intersect(modules$Description, clusters$Description)

```

So.. only 9 overlapping HPO enrichments, and they're all very broad. Perhaps we unlist the genes driving enrichments in the modules and clusters and compare the two that way..

```

# Function to split geneID strings into vectors and remove
# duplicates
split_genes <- function(gene_string) {
  unique(unlist(strsplit(gene_string, split = "[|]")))
}

# Extract and split the genes for modules and clusters
module_genes_list <- lapply(modules$geneID, split_genes)
cluster_genes_list <- lapply(clusters$genes_enrichment, split_genes)

# Flatten the lists and get unique genes
module_genes_unique <- unique(unlist(module_genes_list))
cluster_genes_unique <- unique(unlist(cluster_genes_list))

# Find the intersection (overlap) between the two sets of

```

```

# genes
genes_intersection <- intersect(module_genes_unique, cluster_genes_unique)

# Prepare the summary information
summary_info <- sprintf("Modules: %d, Clusters: %d, Intersection: %d",
  length(module_genes_unique), length(cluster_genes_unique),
  length(genes_intersection))

# Convert the lists to comma-separated strings
module_genes_str <- paste(module_genes_unique, collapse = ", ")
cluster_genes_str <- paste(cluster_genes_unique, collapse = ", ")
genes_intersection_str <- paste(genes_intersection, collapse = ", ")

# Create a combined dataframe
genes_combined_df <- data.frame(Type = c("Module_Genes", "Cluster_Genes",
  "Intersection", "Summary"), Genes = c(module_genes_str, cluster_genes_str,
  genes_intersection_str, summary_info))

# Optionally, save the results to CSV
# write.csv(genes_combined_df, paste0(outdir,
# '/ModvsClust_genes_combined_df_HPO.csv'), row.names =
# FALSE)

# Display or return the combined dataframe
print(genes_combined_df)

```

```

##           Type
## 1 Module_Genes
## 2 Cluster_Genes
## 3 Intersection
## 4           Summary
##
## 1
## 2 ANTXR2, AR, AURKA, BMPR1B, CCND1, COL3A1, EP300, FKBP6, FLT1, GLI3, GNAS, HARS2, KIF14, MKKS, NIPB
## 3
## 4

```

What if we do this for each cell type? So, from significant HPO enrichments, unlist genes driving enrichments for each cell type and look at where they intersect.

```

# Step 1: Extract cell types
clusters$CellType <- gsub("-Cluster_.*", "", clusters$Cluster)
modules$CellType <- gsub("_[^_]*$", "", modules$Cluster)

# Step 2: Aggregate genes by cell type Split and unique
# function for genes
split_genes <- function(gene_string) {
  unique(unlist(strsplit(gene_string, split = "[|]")))
}

# Aggregate genes for clusters
cluster_genes_by_celltype <- clusters %>%
  group_by(CellType) %>%

```

```

summarise(Genes = list(unique(unlist(lapply(genes_enrichment,
      split_genes)))))) %>%
ungroup()

# Aggregate genes for modules
module_genes_by_celltype <- modules %>%
  group_by(CellType) %>%
  summarise(Genes = list(unique(unlist(lapply(geneID, split_genes)))))) %>%
  ungroup()

# Step 3: Compare genes between cell types from clusters
# and modules This assumes a full join to ensure all cell
# types are included, even if they appear in only one
# dataset
comparison <- full_join(cluster_genes_by_celltype, module_genes_by_celltype,
  by = "CellType", suffix = c("_Cluster", "_Module")) %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(Intersection = list(intersect(Genes_Cluster, Genes_Module)),
    Num_Genes_Clusters = length(Genes_Cluster), Num_Genes_Modules = length(Genes_Module),
    Num_Genes_Intersection = length(Intersection), Genes_Cluster = list(Genes_Cluster),
    Genes_Module = list(Genes_Module)) %>%
  ungroup()

comparison <- comparison[c("CellType", "Num_Genes_Clusters",
  "Genes_Cluster", "Num_Genes_Modules", "Genes_Module", "Num_Genes_Intersection",
  "Intersection")]
comparison$Intersection <- lapply(comparison$Intersection, function(x) if (length(x) ==
  0) "NULL" else x)
# make more visually appealing Define a function to
# concatenate gene names or return 'NULL' for empty lists
concat_genes <- function(genes) {
  if (length(genes) == 0) {
    return("NULL")
  } else {
    return(paste(genes, collapse = ", "))
  }
}

# Apply this function to the relevant columns
comparison$Genes_Cluster <- sapply(comparison$Genes_Cluster,
  concat_genes)
comparison$Genes_Module <- sapply(comparison$Genes_Module, concat_genes)
comparison$Intersection <- sapply(comparison$Intersection, concat_genes)

# Optionally, save the comparison to CSV (Note: Lists
# within cells need special handling for CSVs)
# write_csv(comparison,
# paste0(outdir, 'Mod-Clust_celltype_genes_HPO_comparison.csv'))

# Display or use the comparison
print(comparison)

```

```
## # A tibble: 16 x 7
```

```
## CellType Num_Genes_Clusters Genes_Cluster Num_Genes_Modules Genes_Module
## <chr> <int> <chr> <int> <chr>
## 1 Astro 55 ANTXR2, AR, AU~ 0 NULL
## 2 CGE_dev 10 CFHR5, ETS1, H~ 0 NULL
## 3 ID2 129 ACOX1, AKT2, A~ 11 DPH2, DPH5, ~
## 4 L2-3_CUX2 16 CASK, GALM, GY~ 22 HRAS, KRAS, ~
## 5 L4_RORB 34 BACH2, BCL10, ~ 5 IVNS1ABP, S~
## 6 L5-6_THEMIS 21 DLL4, DNAJC30,~ 0 NULL
## 7 LAMP5_NOS1 60 ANAPC1, ARCN1,~ 0 NULL
## 8 MGE_dev 10 IGF1, MAFB, ME~ 6 FLNB, TBX22~
## 9 OPC 7 AGTPBP1, DDB1,~ 0 NULL
## 10 PN_dev 62 AGA, ASH1L, AT~ 0 NULL
## 11 PV 8 ANXA11, HNRNPD~ 0 NULL
## 12 Vas 17 ADA2, ARL6IP6,~ 0 NULL
## 13 Micro 0 NULL 82 PPCS, CPT2, ~
## 14 PV_SCUBE3 0 NULL 26 PTPN22, LHC~
## 15 SST 0 NULL 7 DNAH1, DNAJ~
## 16 VIP 0 NULL 26 CENPF, DISP~
## # i 2 more variables: Num_Genes_Intersection <int>, Intersection <chr>
```

repeat with DGN enrichments

compare the genes driving significant DGN enrichments in the modules and clusters

```
outdir <- "./results/gene_comparisons/"
modules <- read_csv(paste0(outdir, "hdWGCNA_DGN_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv"))
clusters <- read_csv(paste0(outdir, "TCSeq_DGN_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv"))
dis_clust_intersect <- intersect(modules$Description, clusters$Description)
```

Unlist the genes driving enrichments in the modules and clusters and compare the two that way.

```
# Function to split geneID strings into vectors and remove
# duplicates
split_genes <- function(gene_string) {
  unique(unlist(strsplit(gene_string, split = "[/|]")))
}

# Extract and split the genes for modules and clusters
module_genes_list <- lapply(modules$geneID, split_genes)
cluster_genes_list <- lapply(clusters$genes_enrichment, split_genes)

# Flatten the lists and get unique genes
module_genes_unique <- unique(unlist(module_genes_list))
cluster_genes_unique <- unique(unlist(cluster_genes_list))

# Find the intersection (overlap) between the two sets of
# genes
genes_intersection <- intersect(module_genes_unique, cluster_genes_unique)

# Prepare the summary information
summary_info <- sprintf("Modules: %d, Clusters: %d, Intersection: %d",
  length(module_genes_unique), length(cluster_genes_unique),
  length(genes_intersection))
```

```

# Convert the lists to comma-separated strings
module_genes_str <- paste(module_genes_unique, collapse = ", ")
cluster_genes_str <- paste(cluster_genes_unique, collapse = ", ")
genes_intersection_str <- paste(genes_intersection, collapse = ", ")

# Create a combined dataframe
genes_combined_df <- data.frame(Type = c("Module_Genes", "Cluster_Genes",
    "Intersection", "Summary"), Genes = c(module_genes_str, cluster_genes_str,
    genes_intersection_str, summary_info))

# Optionally, save the results to CSV
# write.csv(genes_combined_df, paste0(outdir,
# '/ModusClust_genes_combined_df_DGN.csv'), row.names =
# FALSE)

# Display or return the combined dataframe
print(genes_combined_df)

```

```

##           Type
## 1 Module_Genes
## 2 Cluster_Genes
## 3 Intersection
## 4           Summary
##
## 1
## 2 HES7, NELFA, NSD2, PTCH2, RERE, SIM1, SOX2, SUFU, CXCL8, GRAP2, HSPA4, IL6, POLD1, TNF, ZNF236, ANI
## 3
## 4

```

Do this for each cell type. So, from significant DGN enrichments, unlist genes driving enrichments for each cell type and look at where they intersect.

```

# Step 1: Extract cell types
clusters$CellType <- gsub("-Cluster.*", "", clusters$Cluster)
modules$CellType <- gsub("[^_]*$", "", modules$Cluster)

# Step 2: Aggregate genes by cell type Split and unique
# function for genes
split_genes <- function(gene_string) {
  unique(unlist(strsplit(gene_string, split = "[/|]")))
}

# Aggregate genes for clusters
cluster_genes_by_celltype <- clusters %>%
  group_by(CellType) %>%
  summarise(Genes = list(unique(unlist(lapply(genes_enrichment,
    split_genes)))))) %>%
  ungroup()

# Aggregate genes for modules
module_genes_by_celltype <- modules %>%
  group_by(CellType) %>%

```

```

summarise(Genes = list(unique(unlist(lapply(geneID, split_genes)))))) %>%
ungroup()

# Step 3: Compare genes between cell types from clusters
# and modules This assumes a full join to ensure all cell
# types are included, even if they appear in only one
# dataset
comparison <- full_join(cluster_genes_by_celltype, module_genes_by_celltype,
  by = "CellType", suffix = c("_Cluster", "_Module")) %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(Intersection = list(intersect(Genes_Cluster, Genes_Module)),
    Num_Genes_Clusters = length(Genes_Cluster), Num_Genes_Modules = length(Genes_Module),
    Num_Genes_Intersection = length(Intersection), Genes_Cluster = list(Genes_Cluster),
    Genes_Module = list(Genes_Module)) %>%
  ungroup()

comparison <- comparison[c("CellType", "Num_Genes_Clusters",
  "Genes_Cluster", "Num_Genes_Modules", "Genes_Module", "Num_Genes_Intersection",
  "Intersection")]
comparison$Intersection <- lapply(comparison$Intersection, function(x) if (length(x) ==
  0) "NULL" else x)
# make more visually appealing Define a function to
# concatenate gene names or return 'NULL' for empty lists
concat_genes <- function(genes) {
  if (length(genes) == 0) {
    return("NULL")
  } else {
    return(paste(genes, collapse = ", "))
  }
}

# Apply this function to the relevant columns
comparison$Genes_Cluster <- sapply(comparison$Genes_Cluster,
  concat_genes)
comparison$Genes_Module <- sapply(comparison$Genes_Module, concat_genes)
comparison$Intersection <- sapply(comparison$Intersection, concat_genes)

# Optionally, save the comparison to CSV (Note: Lists
# within cells need special handling for CSVs)
# write_csv(comparison,
# paste0(outdir, 'Mod-Clust_celltype_genes_DGN_comparison.csv'))

# Display or use the comparison
print(comparison)

```

```

## # A tibble: 16 x 7
##   CellType   Num_Genes_Clusters Genes_Cluster   Num_Genes_Modules Genes_Module
##   <chr>           <int> <chr>           <int> <chr>
## 1 Astro             15 HES7, NELFA, N~      15 HCRTR1, TAC~
## 2 ID2                82 ANKH, MESP2, P~        6 AGT, IL15, ~
## 3 L4_RORB           30 ALB, BMP2, ENA~      44 VHL, COQ2, ~
## 4 L5-6_THEMIS        8 ADAM10, ADRA2A~     58 GABPA, VHL,~
## 5 MGE_dev           14 ALG13, AP4B1, ~        0 NULL

```

```
## 6 Micro          19 ATP6VOA4, CLEC~          0 NULL
## 7 PN_dev         106 EGFR, NOTCH1, ~          15 CELA3B, CFH~
## 8 PV             25 ABCC6, APOB, B~          0 NULL
## 9 PV_SCUBE3      9 CDKN1A, EBAG9,~          60 NFKB1, IL15~
## 10 SST           321 ATXN2, EIF2B1,~          43 HES1, HBEGF~
## 11 VIP           78 ACYP2, ADGRB3,~          32 RMDN2, TIMM~
## 12 CGE_dev       0 NULL          82 OSCP1, PTPN~
## 13 L2-3_CUX2     0 NULL          27 ADORA1, SMC~
## 14 L5-6_TLE4     0 NULL          31 EPAS1, RASS~
## 15 LAMP5_NOS1    0 NULL          14 FKBP5, CYP3~
## 16 Vas           0 NULL          10 PIK3CD, CD3~
## # i 2 more variables: Num_Genes_Intersection <int>, Intersection <chr>
```

6. Overlap in HPO enrichments between disease gene lists and co-expression modules and clusters

```
HPO_enrich <- read.csv("./scratch/sanitycheck/enrichments/neuropsych_genelist_enrichments_HPO_0.05padj_
# Filter the dataframe for descriptions that appear more
# than once
descriptions_by_cluster <- HPO_enrich %>%
  group_by(Cluster) %>%
  summarise(Descriptions = list(unique(Description))) %>%
  deframe()

Disgene_enrich <- HPO_enrich$Description
# read in the co-expression module enrichments
Coexp_HPO <- read.csv("./results/gene_comparisons/hdWGCNA_HPO_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv")
Coexp_HPO <- Coexp_HPO$Description

# calculate intersect of HPO terms between co-expression
# modules and disease gene list HPO term enrichments
intersect_discoexp <- unique(intersect(Coexp_HPO, Disgene_enrich))
length(intersect_discoexp)

## [1] 71
```

```
# Determine which clusters are contributing to these
# overlapping terms
contributing_clusters <- lapply(names(descriptions_by_cluster),
  function(cluster) {
    overlapping_terms <- intersect(descriptions_by_cluster[[cluster]],
      intersect_discoexp)
    if (length(overlapping_terms) > 0) {
      return(data.frame(Cluster = cluster, Description = overlapping_terms))
    } else {
      return(NULL)
    }
  })
```

```

# Combine the results into a single dataframe
contributing_disgeneL <- do.call(rbind, contributing_clusters)

# Print the contributing clusters and their descriptions
print(contributing_disgeneL)

```

```

##           Cluster                               Description
## 1  SNV_neurodev                Abnormal lip morphology
## 2  SNV_neurodev                Abnormal upper lip morphology
## 3  SNV_neurodev                Abnormal cardiac septum morphology
## 4  SNV_neurodev                Abnormality of the philtrum
## 5  SNV_neurodev                Abnormal nasal bridge morphology
## 6  SNV_neurodev                Ventricular septal defect
## 7  SNV_neurodev                Abnormal ventricular septum morphology
## 8  SNV_neurodev                Abnormal jaw morphology
## 9  SNV_neurodev                Abnormal location of ears
## 10 SNV_neurodev                Tooth malposition
## 11 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal mandible morphology
## 12 SNV_neurodev                Abnormality of the dentition
## 13 SNV_neurodev                Deviation of finger
## 14 SNV_neurodev                Deviation of the hand or of fingers of the hand
## 15 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal morphology of the nasal alae
## 16 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal hair quantity
## 17 SNV_neurodev                Short digit
## 18 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal toe morphology
## 19 SNV_neurodev                Low-set ears
## 20 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal cerebral ventricle morphology
## 21 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal nostril morphology
## 22 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal dermatoglyphics
## 23 SNV_neurodev                Anteverted nares
## 24 SNV_neurodev                Atrial septal defect
## 25 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal atrial septum morphology
## 26 SNV_neurodev                Depressed nasal bridge
## 27 SNV_neurodev                Ventriculomegaly
## 28 SNV_neurodev                Micrognathia
## 29 SNV_neurodev                Aplasia/hypoplasia affecting bones of the axial skeleton
## 30 SNV_neurodev                Aplasia/Hypoplasia of the mandible
## 31 SNV_neurodev                Aplasia/Hypoplasia involving bones of the skull
## 32 SNV_neurodev                Aplasia/hypoplasia of the extremities
## 33 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal cardiac atrium morphology
## 34 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal palmar dermatoglyphics
## 35 SNV_neurodev                Abnormality of dental morphology
## 36 SNV_neurodev                Abnormality of the palmar creases
## 37 SNV_neurodev                Regional abnormality of skin
## 38 SNV_neurodev                Abnormality of the fontanelles or cranial sutures
## 39 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal palm morphology
## 40 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal skin morphology of the palm
## 41 SNV_neurodev                Abnormal neck morphology
## 42 SNV_neurodev                Brachydactyly
## 43 SNV_neurodev                Abnormality of the neck
## 44 SNV_neurodev                Aplasia/Hypoplasia of the cerebellum
## 45 SNV_neurodev                Sparse hair
## 46 SNV_neurodev                Abnormality of skin pigmentation

```

```

## 47 SNV_neurodev Irregular hyperpigmentation
## 48 SNV_neurodev Abnormality of the nail
## 49 SNV_neurodev Abnormal fear/anxiety-related behavior
## 50 SNV_neurodev Localized skin lesion
## 51 SNV_neurodev Abnormal hindbrain morphology
## 52 SNV_neurodev Abnormal metencephalon morphology
## 53 SNV_neurodev Abnormal upper limb bone morphology
## 54 SNV_neurodev Hyperpigmentation of the skin
## 55 SNV_neurodev Abnormal cerebellum morphology
## 56 SNV_neurol Abnormal hindbrain morphology
## 57 SNV_neurol Abnormal metencephalon morphology
## 58 SNV_neurol Abnormal cerebellum morphology
## 59 SNV_neurol Atrophy/Degeneration affecting the central nervous system
## 60 SNV_neurol Abnormal peripheral nervous system morphology
## 61 SNV_neurol Abnormal cerebral cortex morphology
## 62 SNV_neurol Reduced tendon reflexes
## 63 SNV_neurol Dystonia
## 64 SNV_neurol Peripheral neuropathy
## 65 SNV_neurol Aplasia/Hypoplasia of the cerebellum
## 66 SNV_neurol Depression
## 67 SNV_neurol Abnormal cerebral ventricle morphology
## 68 SNV_neurol Ventriculomegaly
## 69 SNV_neurol Impairment in personality functioning
## 70 SNV_neurol Cerebral cortical atrophy
## 71 SNV_neurol Age of death
## 72 SNV_neurol Mortality/Aging
## 73 SNV_neurol Cerebral calcification
## 74 SNV_neurol Abnormal temporal lobe morphology
## 75 SNV_neurol Positional foot deformity
## 76 SNV_neurol Talipes
## 77 SNV_neurol Ectopic calcification

```

```

# Repeat with TCseq cluster HPO enrichments
clust_HPO <- read.csv("./results/gene_comparisons/TCSeq_HPO_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv")
clust_HPO <- clust_HPO$Description

# calculate intersect of HPO terms between temporal
# expression clusters and disease gene list HPO term
# enrichments
intersect_disclust <- unique(intersect(clust_HPO, Disgene_enrich))
length(intersect_disclust)

```

```
## [1] 35
```

```

# Determine which clusters are contributing to these
# overlapping terms
contributing_clusters <- lapply(names(descriptions_by_cluster),
  function(cluster) {
    overlapping_terms <- intersect(descriptions_by_cluster[[cluster]],
      intersect_disclust)
    if (length(overlapping_terms) > 0) {
      return(data.frame(Cluster = cluster, Description = overlapping_terms))
    } else {

```

```

        return(NULL)
    }
})

# Combine the results into a single dataframe
contributing_disgeneL <- do.call(rbind, contributing_clusters)

# Print the contributing clusters and their descriptions
print(contributing_disgeneL)

```

##	Cluster	Description
## 1	SNV_neurodev	Delayed speech and language development
## 2	SNV_neurodev	Language impairment
## 3	SNV_neurodev	Abnormal communication
## 4	SNV_neurodev	Feeding difficulties
## 5	SNV_neurodev	Abnormal hair morphology
## 6	SNV_neurodev	Abnormality of upper lip vermillion
## 7	SNV_neurodev	Decreased head circumference
## 8	SNV_neurodev	Microcephaly
## 9	SNV_neurodev	Absent speech
## 10	SNV_neurodev	Ventricular septal defect
## 11	SNV_neurodev	Abnormal repetitive mannerisms
## 12	SNV_neurodev	Restricted or repetitive behaviors or interests
## 13	SNV_neurodev	Abnormal ventricular septum morphology
## 14	SNV_neurodev	Abnormality of mouth shape
## 15	SNV_neurodev	Feeding difficulties in infancy
## 16	SNV_neurodev	Plagiocephaly
## 17	SNV_neurodev	Atrial septal defect
## 18	SNV_neurodev	Abnormal atrial septum morphology
## 19	SNV_neurodev	Abnormality of the breast
## 20	SNV_neurodev	Abnormal breast morphology
## 21	SNV_neurodev	Downturned corners of mouth
## 22	SNV_neurodev	Abnormal cardiac atrium morphology
## 23	SNV_neurodev	Displacement of the urethral meatus
## 24	SNV_neurodev	Hypospadias
## 25	SNV_neurodev	Highly arched eyebrow
## 26	SNV_neurodev	Abnormal male urethral meatus morphology
## 27	SNV_neurodev	Low posterior hairline
## 28	SNV_neurodev	Abnormality of the posterior hairline
## 29	SNV_neurodev	Abnormality of the urethra
## 30	SNV_neurodev	Widely spaced teeth
## 31	SNV_neurodev	Sleep disturbance
## 32	SNV_neurodev	Facial hypotonia
## 33	SNV_neurol	Morphological abnormality of the pyramidal tract
## 34	SNV_neurol	Apnea
## 35	SNV_neurol	Profound global developmental delay
## 36	SNV_neurol	Microcephaly
## 37	SNV_neurol	Decreased head circumference
## 38	SNV_neurol	Feeding difficulties in infancy